

Accelerating Big Data Initiatives and interactive visualizations within the public sector

Manu Sud^a

^a*Toronto, Ontario, Canada*

Keywords:

1. Introduction

A successful big data program needs support across the organization, all divisions and senior management. This presentation will provide information on how to gain traction for big data by conveying the value to your stakeholders. As an analytics and policy team in the provincial government, we empower policy advisors to accelerate policy development and support evidenced-based decision-making by integrating GIS in analytics. Understanding the complexities in energy use is essential towards energy program delivery, conservation and long-term planning. GIS enables people to gain regional understanding on challenging energy issue

2. Aim

To provide insights on how to create big data champions, gain employee and management support and demonstrate the ROI of big data initiatives.

3. Material and methods

Survey conducted within the Ministry to evaluate data and analytics need.

4. Results

1. 100% Of respondents use maps and analytics for internal briefings
2. 67% Of respondents work with energy consumption data
3. 75% Of respondents are interested in static maps
4. 25% are interested in interactive web maps

Taking these requests, we built vision in the team to design clear and accurate data visualizations support for strong policy development. Both spatial and data analytics are essential for providing a provincial level perspective with on-the-ground details. Answering questions such as how does energy consumption compare across different regions of Ontario is important for policy initiatives.

January 22, 2018

5. Conclusions

This presentation will explain use of analytics in the government. In addition, it will focus on how geographical information system (GIS) can be built within an analytics and policy team and the advantages of GIS on policy interpretation and application from three aspects: 1) implementing GIS and analytics for policy development, 2) recognizing the value and achievements, and 3) promoting analytics together for policy innovation. As the team navigates into the future trends and needs, it will leverage machine learning, design thinking and analysis based on cost-benefit.

The tool we recently developed is

<http://moenergy.maps.arcgis.com/apps/MapJournal/index.html?appid=0905e3acaf58478ebb7c50bb7>

I will talk about our challenges and how interactive tools help in the government.

6. Keywords

Energy, Innovation, Analytics, Mapping, Design Thinking

Author biography

Manu Sud Ontario Ministry of Energy